

IMPACT OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING AND SELF-EFFICACY ON MATHEMATICS PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

Educators are recommended to prioritize the enhancement of prospective teachers' mathematics pedagogical content knowledge (MPCK). Therefore, this study aimed to investigate impact of project-based learning (PjBL) and self-efficacy on MPCK of prospective teachers. It was conducted during the 2023/2023 academic year in Manado, Indonesia, using a quasi-experimental study design. The experimental group was subjected to PjBL, and traditional method was adopted for the control group. MPCK data were collected through essay and performance tests, while self-efficacy was assessed using a 5-point Likert Scale. Subsequently, the data were analyzed using two-way ANOVA. The results showed that (1) Prospective teachers who engaged in PjBL had higher MPCK abilities compared to those subjected to traditional method, (2) There was an interaction between learning methods and self-efficacy, (3) Prospective teachers with high self-efficacy had higher MPCK abilities when subjected to PjBL than traditional method, and vice versa. In conclusion, self-efficacy played a crucial role in the implementation of PjBL for developing knowledge and pedagogical abilities of prospective teachers.

Keywords: Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge; Project-Based Learning; Self-Efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Professional teachers are essential for effective mathematics education, particularly at the elementary level, where basic knowledge and abilities with long-term impact on students' mathematics abilities are instilled. Prospective teachers are expected to attain a level of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) to become proficient educators. Moreover, PCK includes an understanding of the curriculum, students' characteristics, and teaching methods (Demirdögen, 2016; Usak et al., 2022). Studies showed that professional development had a significant impact on PCK, thereby improving teachers performance and students achievement (Hill & Chin, 2018). Inadequate PCK can lead to poor students' performance, confusion, and educational challenges Mathematics pedagogical content knowledge (MPCK) includes familiarity with fundamental mathematics concepts, practical applications, appropriate learning models, and the cognitive development of students (Dunekacke et al., 2015). Bradbury et al. (2018) defined MPCK as the abilities to integrate mathematics and PCK into learning process, an ability set essential for both practicing and aspiring teachers. Elementary school education is responsible for preparing prospective teachers with mathematics knowledge and the abilities to teach mathematics. Observations from field practice showed that prospective teachers struggled with MPCK. Even though some had

strong conceptual and procedural knowledge of mathematics, a significant number lacked pedagogical abilities, and vice versa. This was in accordance with Depaepe et al. (2015), that prospective elementary school teachers struggled to identify mathematics models for problem solving. Similarly, Ramaligela et al. (2019) found that most pre-service teachers of mathematics had limited MPCK abilities, with many struggling to articulate subject knowledge or students' characteristics.

Prospective elementary schools play an important role in ensuring effective learning experiences for students. As a result, prospective teachers had comprehensive training and a thorough understanding of elementary mathematics. MPCK is not instantaneous, rather, it evolves through continuous and systematic learning efforts starting from undergraduate studies in PGSD and extending into roles as elementary school teachers (Kadarisma et al., 2019). Several studies have been conducted on MPCK, with Ramaligela et al. (2019) specifically using Cycle 9E learning to develop PCK for prospective teachers. The results showed that pre-service teachers were proficient in subject matter and technology integration, but lacked PCK, particularly in collaboratively developing effective learning strategies for specific concepts. Similarly, Aksu & Kul (2019) investigated the relationship between efficacy, anxiety, and PCK among prospective mathematics teachers, and noted that high MPCK could increase MTE (Mathematics teaching efficacy) and decrease MTA (Mathematics Teaching Anxiety) among both in-service and pre-service teachers. However, further empirical studies are required since this study is based on a survey. There is a dearth of information regarding the development of MPCK among prospective teachers despite several investigations. Therefore, this current study explored the implementation of project-based learning (PjBL) in elementary teachers' education. PjBL is a learning model known to enhance students' engagement and improve learning outcomes of affective, cognitive, and students' abilities (Guo et al., 2020), as well as motivation and collaboration (Shin, 2018). It is based on real-world problems that are relevant to students' interests and helps foster critical analysis and application of knowledge in problem-solving contexts. Facilitated by teachers, PjBL promotes the framing of pertinent questions, construction of meaningful assignments, the development of cognitive and social abilities, as well as accurate assessment of students' learning experiences (Efstratia, 2014).

This current study aimed to investigate the effect of PjBL on prospective teachers' MPCK, with self-efficacy as a predictor. The research questions are as follows:

- 1) Is there a significant difference in MPCK abilities between prospective teachers who instructed through PjBL versus traditional method?
- 2) Is there any interaction between the learning model and self-efficacy?
- 3) Is there a significant difference between prospective teachers who instructed in PjBL versus traditional method for students with high self-efficacy?
- 4) Is there a significant difference between prospective teachers who instructed in PjBL versus traditional method for students with low self-efficacy?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge (MPCK)

PCK is a crucial knowledge that enables teachers or prospective teachers to effectively convey subject to students. It is also defined as the incorporation of unique pedagogic knowledge of teachers as a distinguishing feature of professional understanding. Pioneered by Shulman (Demirdöğen, 2016; Ramaligela et al., 2019), PCK combines subject matter and PCK to facilitate classroom instruction and implementation.

Shulman (1987) identified three areas of knowledge required for effective learning. First, a thorough understanding of content knowledge. Second, PCK, specifically for understanding learning models, strategies, and methods for refining teaching practices and experiences. Third, PCK for understanding the subject matter, as well as other pedagogic resources that optimize students learning outcomes (Hwang et al., 2018).

In elementary school mathematics education, the emphasis is on mathematics content knowledge, comprising both conceptual and procedural understanding. Both teachers and students require this knowledge in order to develop mathematics problem-solving strategies. According to Yurniwati & Kustandi (2022), mathematics content knowledge is the development of conceptual and procedural knowledge of mathematics that are interrelated and bidirectional. Conceptual knowledge of mathematics includes an understanding of concepts (Rittle-Johnson, 2017), as well as the structure and relation between concepts (Zuya, 2017).

Procedural knowledge refers to the set of rules or steps used to solve problems through mathematics presentations (Van de Walle et al., 2019), such as symbols, notations, equations, graphs, tables, sentences, and more. Conceptual knowledge serves as the foundation for procedural knowledge, and it shows the importance of teaching conceptual understanding before delving into procedural methods. A profound conceptual understanding enables students to devise problem-solving strategies, fostering connections between mathematics ideas. Consequently, students with strong conceptual understanding typically have good procedural abilities (Rittle-Johnson & Schneider, 2014).

MPCK is the expertise required for effective teaching, including an understanding of the interconnectedness of concepts and the methodologies for problem-solving (Leavy et al., 2015). Darling-Hammond (2017) observed the significance of discipline-specific PCK and the need for teachers to comprehensibly present topics to students across various disciplines. Prospective teachers should not only have a deep understanding of mathematics content but also the capacity to teach effectively. This includes the abilities to plan, implement, and evaluate learning outcomes (Guler & Celik, 2021).

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is a construct that focuses on an individual assessment of the capacity to accomplish tasks successfully in a specific context (Waddington, 2023). It significantly affects the method, attitude, abilities acquisition, activity selection, and perseverance in

pursuing goals (Liaw & Huang, 2013). According to Liu et al. (2023), self-efficacy influences students behavior and persistence, attitude in the face of adversity, as well as mode of thought and emotional response, thereby shaping motivation, cognition, and behavior.

Individuals with high self-efficacy are inclined to set increasingly challenging goals upon achieving success (Kodden, 2020). Conversely, failure to attain set objectives can diminish self-efficacy, motivation, and the probability of future accomplishments. Those with high self-efficacy have greater resilience to failure compared to counterparts with low self-efficacy (Hussain & Khan, 2022).

Usher & Schunk (2018) advocated for self-efficacy actions among individuals with high self-efficacy, such as goals setting, adopting effective learning strategies, monitoring progress, and creating conducive physical and social learning environments. Self-efficacy can be affected by various behavioral, social/environmental factors, including completion of tasks, perceived progress, social comparisons, and feedback from teachers and coaches (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2021).

In an educational context, teachers with high self-efficacy create environments conducive to students motivation and goal-oriented, thereby providing effective teaching outcomes (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001). CeriT (2010) found that high teachers self-efficacy indicated willingness to support, implement, and create positive change, as well as perseverance during challenges, openness to new ideas, and abilities to experiment with novel teaching strategies. Meanwhile, teachers with low self-efficacy tend to avoid challenging activities, make excuses, perceive challenging tasks as insurmountable, focus on negative consequences, and eventually lose confidence in personal abilities (Cherry, 2020).

Project-Based Learning (PjBL)

PjBL is a student-centered form of instruction that is based on three constructivist principles, namely contextual learning, active students' participation, and knowledge acquisition through social interactions and knowledge sharing (Cain & Cocco, 2013). Students create products in PjBL to represent new understanding, knowledge, and attitudes (Helle et al., 2006). This inquiry-based instructional method fosters knowledge construction through the completion of authentic projects and the creation of real-world products (Brundiers & Wiek, 2013; Guo et al., 2020).

Central to PjBL is the generation of questions driving the project, with students collaborating to develop and present the product as responses. The product includes videos, reports, models, designs, and other artifacts (Holubova, 2008; Kokotsaki et al., 2016). This method promotes cooperative and research-based learning, indicating active students' engagement and comparative learning (Almulla, 2020; Loyens et al., 2015). Students who learn using PjBL typically collaborate to solve a specific problem, create a product for a specific audience, as well as evaluate project and development process (Kokotsaki et al., 2016).

Krajcik & Shin (2014) identified six PjBL principles: a driving question, a focus on learning objectives, participation in educational activities, students' collaboration, the use of

scaffolding technologies, and the creation of tangible artifacts. Students are required to collaborate to solve authentic problems as part of the knowledge integration, application, and construction process. Teachers and community members (e.g., clients) typically act as facilitators, providing feedback and support to students and assist learning process. According to Zhang & Ma (2023), PjBL is dependent on the subject area, course type, academic period, group size, class size, and treatment period. Numerous studies showed that PjBL could enhance students learning.

PjBL produces superior learning outcomes compared to direct instruction (Cheng et al., 2019), fostering motivation, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, and communication abilities (Zhang & Ma, 2023). It also positively influences students intrinsic motivation to learn (Zhang, 2021), and enhances creative thinking abilities (Biazus & Mahtari, 2022). According to Häkkinen et al. (2017) PjBL method is an effective way to develop 21st-century abilities, including critical thinking, problem-solving, interpersonal communication, information and media literacy, cooperation, leadership, teamwork, innovation, and creativity. Implementing PjBL in teachers' preparation programs facilitates the seamless integration of theory and practice, and positively influences professional, academic, and personal abilities (Alrajeh, 2021). It also provides authentic learning environments, field experiences, and continuous feedback, all contributing to students' self-efficacy. Consequently, the model provides preservice science teachers with authentic experiences (Ilyas & Saeed, 2021).

METHOD

This study adopted a quantitative and quasi-experimental methods, without random sampling, and adhered to research ethics to minimize risks and losses for participants (Cash et al., 2016). A quasi-experimental design of 2×2 factorial arrangement was adopted, with PjBL and the traditional method serving as independent variables, MPCK abilities as the dependent variable, and self-efficacy as the moderator.

Experimental study was conducted during the first semester of the academic year 2023/2024 on 2512 prospective teachers enrolled in the Education Faculty of Universitas Manado, Indonesia. Purposive sampling method was adopted, focusing on population characteristics and study objectives (Rai & Thapa, 2015). Intentional sampling ensured homogeneity of samples (Etikan, 2016), enabling study experts to select subjects capable of providing relevant and valuable information (Kelly in Campbell et al., 2020). The sample comprised 64 prospective students (59 female, 5 male) enrolled in Mathematics Education for Elementary Students course, divided into experimental and control groups. This study spanned eight sessions, focusing on the teaching and learning of arithmetics for elementary students.

The experimental group learned using PjBL, while the control group adopted the traditional method (Table. 1). Prior to treatment implementation in the experimental and control classes, perception equalization was carried out with lecturers familiarizing students with the steps of PjBL and expository models. Students were also informed about the goals and expectations of the learning model implementation. Learning was carried out in 8 (eight) sessions, with each lasting 150 minutes.

Table 1: Treatment for Experimental and Control Groups

Session	Experimental Group	Control Group
1-2	Prospective teachers explore arithmetics using learning tools.	Educators explain and demonstrate arithmetics using learning tools.
3	Prospective teachers observe and analyze the process of learning mathematics in elementary schools.	Prospective teachers are trained and effective in making learning media.
4	Prospective teachers plan projects, as well as design learning media and lesson plans.	Prospective teachers create learning media and lesson plans.
5-6	Prospective teachers implement projects by conducting teaching practices with elementary school students. Educators assess prospective teachers' performance.	peer teaching educators assess prospective teachers' performance.
7	Prospective teachers teaching practice videos and discussions.	Class discussion.
8	MPCK essay test.	MPCK essay test.

Educators initially explained and demonstrated arithmetics using various learning tools, subsequently followed by observations and analysis at schools. Prospective teachers were trained and tasked with developing learning media planning projects, as well as designing lesson plans. Projects were implemented by conducting teaching practices with elementary school students. These teaching practices were recorded as videos and subsequently evaluated. Two types of data were obtained in this study, namely MPCK and self-efficacy. MPCK abilities were assessed using a performance test and an essay test. The performance test evaluated prospective teachers' abilities to teach mathematics effectively using various teaching tools, enabling students to actively acquire knowledge. The essay test (8 questions) assessed: 1) conceptual knowledge; 2) procedural knowledge; and 3) PCK. Instruments validity was confirmed through Pearson product moment correlation, where eight of the ten questions were valid with construct values ranging from 0.592 to 0.919. The Alpha Cronbach reliability score for all eight items was 0.883, falling within the “good” category, with each item scoring a minimum of 0.8. Self-efficacy data were obtained through a questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). The questionnaire comprised 40 items, namely (1) mastery experiences; (2) vicarious experiences; (3) verbal persuasion; and (4) physiological and affective states. Out of the 40 items, 39 were deemed valid, with Pearson correlation value ranging from 0.4331 to 0.761. The reliability test result confirmed through Alpha Cronbach was 0.942, categorized as “good”. MPCK data were subsequently analyzed using a two-way ANOVA, and all data were assessed using JASP 0.18.2.

RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for prospective teachers' responses to MPCK. In the experimental group, teachers with high self-efficacy ($M= 91.89$; $SD= 2.713$) had higher MPCK abilities than those with low self-efficacy. Conversely, in the control group, prospective teachers with high self-efficacy ($M= 65.78$; $SD= 6.690$) had better MPCK abilities than those with low self-efficacy ($M= 78.22$; $SD= 9.550$).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistic

Groups	SE	Mean	SD	N
Experimental	High	91,89	2,713	9
	Low	61,89	7,507	9
	Total	80,14	12,975	34
Traditional method	High	65,78	6,960	9
	Low	78,22	9,550	9
	Total	70,55	7,837	34

Two-way ANOVA was conducted to address the research question (Table. 3). The homogeneity of MPCK was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk test ($F=0.953$ ($p\text{-value} = 0.134$), and normality was determined using Levene Test ($F= 1.82$, $p\text{-value}= 0.163$). These tests showed that the data had homogeneous variances and originated from a normally distributed population.

Table 3: Two-way ANOVA

Cases	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Methods	215.845	1	215.845	4.266	0.047
SE	718.687	1	718.687	14.204	< .001
SE * Methods	4029.076	1	4029.076	79.630	< .001
Residuals	1619.119	32	50.597		

Based on the teaching method, there was a statistically significant differences in prospective teachers MPCK between the experimental and control groups ($F=4.266$, $p\text{-value} =0.047$). This showed that PjBL contributed to an increase in future teachers MPCK. Furthermore, there was a significant difference in MPCK based on self-efficacy ($F = 4.27$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$), and an interaction between teaching methods and self-efficacy ($F= 79.63$; $P\text{-value} < .0.01$).

Figure 1: Descriptive Plots

Prospective teachers with high self-efficacy in the experimental group had greater MPCK abilities, while those with low self-efficacy in the control group showed higher abilities. Post

hoc Tuckey test (Table 4) was used to determine the difference in prospective teachers' MPCK according to self-efficacy.

Table 4: Post Hoc Comparisons

		Mean Difference	SE	t	P _{Tukey}
High PjBL	Low PjBL	30.094	3.353	8.975	< .001
	High Traditional	26.056	3.353	7.770	< .001
	Low Traditional	13.833	3.353	4.125	0.001
Low PjBL	High Traditional	-4.039	3.353	-1.204	0.629
	Low Traditional	-16.261	3.353	-4.849	< .001
High Traditional	Low Traditional	-12.222	3.353	-3.645	0.005

There were significant differences between high self-efficacy and prospective teachers' MPCK abilities acquired through PjBL and traditional method ($t = 8.975$, $p < 0.001$). This showed teachers with high self-efficacy were more suited to learning through PjBL than traditional method. However, those with low self-efficacy had higher MPCK when learning through the traditional method rather than PjBL.

DISCUSSION

There was a significant difference in MPCK abilities between prospective teachers who were subjected to PjBL and those that used traditional method

Two-way ANOVA showed significant differences in prospective teachers' MPCK abilities between the experimental and control groups. Prospective teachers in the experimental group had higher MPCK abilities than counterparts in control group, indicating that PjBL improved MPCK compared to traditional method. MPCK development was demonstrated by increasing students' conceptual and procedural knowledge, a prerequisite element supporting proficiency in teaching whole number concepts. The results were supported by (Depaepe et al., 2018) that the gap in understanding concepts and teaching whole numbers to elementary school students could be addressed by commencing with conceptual knowledge. Similarly, it was suggested that MPCK abilities could be maximized by thoroughly mastering conceptual understanding.

Students subjected to PjBL treatment had higher MPCK abilities due to active engagement in elementary school observations during the project analysis stage and activity planning. These observations aimed to analyze elementary school students conceptual and procedural knowledge needs, as well as teaching abilities, regarding number materials. Subsequently, students deliberated on project planning based on number concept materials, fostering an investigation into how content knowledge evolved in accordance with children development principles. According to Guo et al. (2020), PjBL enhances knowledge, concepts, and abilities in students' learning processes and outcomes.

Studies showed that students undergoing PjBL could select teaching tools based on learning objectives, teaching methods, worksheets, and assessments. These capabilities were developed during project design and development stages, where students engaged in

discussions regarding procedural knowledge and appropriate teaching methods. Parrado-Martínez and Sánchez-Andújar (2020) stated that PjBL could enhance teamwork, communication, creativity, and task organization abilities.

Students exposed to PjBL showed significant improvement in pedagogical abilities when teaching number concepts after conducting teaching practices with elementary schools. In essence, students could select teaching aids, create learning activities, as well as communicate and collaborate with teachers. König et al. (2015) argued that direct teaching experience in teachers' education programs facilitated the development of mathematics teaching abilities.

PjBL enables students to apply projects directly to elementary school settings. Manandhar (2018) explained that applying PjBL outside of the classroom could facilitate students' authentic understanding of materials when confronted with real-world problems. In the final stage of PjBL, namely presentation and reflection, students showed abilities to deliver and integrate projects into elementary school learning processes.

Moreover, the strengths and weaknesses of the projects were evaluated through group presentations. This fostered the sharing of opinions and ideas with one another through productive communication, as well as the abilities to create better future projects. Discussion activities at the presentation and reflection stages were consistent with Guo et al. (2020), which showed the importance of product manufacturing in integrating and reconstructing knowledge, discovering professional abilities, improving communication, as well as instilling interest and discipline.

Studies showed that prospective teachers with high self-efficacy did not develop effectively when exposed to traditional method. According to Rinke et al. (2016), prospective teachers instructed through an expository model had lower teaching abilities and materials mastery than those using active learning method. For traditional method, students do not have the opportunity to develop conceptual, procedural knowledge, and abilities in teaching independently or in groups. Lecturers typically explain material directly and explicitly, depriving students the opportunity to develop knowledge and express ideas. This was consistent with Barendsen and Henze (2019), stating that the dominant role of teachers in the classroom contributed to students limited conceptual knowledge and the prevalence of misconceptions. In such environments, opportunities are not given to explore conceptual and procedural knowledge in accordance with the needs of elementary students.

There was interaction between learning model and self-efficacy

This current study showed an interaction between learning models (PjBL and traditional method) and self-efficacy (high and low), suggesting that these factors collectively influenced prospective teachers' efficacy. Students with high self-efficacy actively engaged in learning process were confident in planning learning materials or media, and motivated to participate in teaching practice projects and teamwork.

Prospective teachers with high self-efficacy were willing to directly participate in difficult learning tasks and devise effective strategies. This advantage of high self-efficacy was accommodated by PjBL, where students could be more inspiring, creative, and innovative when planning learning materials and tools, carrying out teaching practice projects, or fostering good teamwork. This was similar to Shin (2018), indicating that high self-efficacy positively correlated with the use of PjBL.

Moreover, teamwork could motivate students to actively participate in extracurricular projects and improve English abilities. Alt (2015) showed that students with high self-efficacy in constructivist learning were more motivated to build and reflect on academic knowledge, as well as manage learning process effectively. In contrast, students with low self-efficacy were less confident in the abilities to organize or manage learning, resulting in low conceptual and procedural knowledge. During teaching practice, students often experienced anxiety, fear of failure, and lack confidence in adapting to classroom conditions. Those with low SE were less active in project planning discussions, and less comfortable using PjBL. Furthermore, in teaching practice activities, there was limited mastery of materials, leading to misconceptions and ineffective classroom management.

There was a significant difference between prospective teachers who were subjected to PjBL and those that used traditional method, particularly among students with high self-efficacy

There was a significant increase in MPCK abilities in the context of high self-efficacy learned with PjBL compared to traditional method. Students showed MPCK development in terms of conceptual and procedural knowledge, specifically in the abilities to establish relationship between number concepts in daily life and design appropriate problem-solving procedures. Aspects of teaching abilities had also evolved, including the use of learning strategies and appropriate media, as well as the abilities to evaluate or reflect on number concepts in elementary schools.

The development of MPCK could be attributed to PjBL emphasis on active participation of students in analyzing phenomena related to the number concepts, facilitating the correlation of number concepts with practical teaching scenarios. In addition, students could design teaching aids, such as learning media, for use in teaching practice, as well as create instructional videos for presentation and evaluation. PjBl is relevant for students with high self-efficacy due to confidence in the abilities to complete planning tasks and implement teaching practices responsibly, embracing feedback for improvements. This was supported by Bjerke and Solomon (2020), which showed the necessity of high self-efficacy among prospective teachers for effective mathematics instruction.

Prospective teachers with high self-efficacy were less capable of developing conceptual and procedural knowledge, and struggled to explain the interrelationship between abstract concepts, resulting in ineffective teaching strategies during simulations. This was because the expository model failed to foster active students' participation, leading to reduced motivation and engagement.

Consequently, when engaged in simulation activities, students faced challenges with creativity and implementing effective learning strategies due to limited opportunities to discuss and discover new sources of information. In line with Yıldız and Özdemir (2019), students with high self-efficacy in mathematics learning required successful learning experience to stimulate active participation. Özben and Kilicoglu (2021) showed that high self-efficacy students might struggle with learning due to ineffective teaching methods.

There was a significant difference between prospective teachers who were subjected to PjBL and those that used traditional method, particularly among students with low self-efficacy

Prospective teachers with low self-efficacy had better MPCK abilities when exposed to traditional method rather than PjBL. This was because the expository model provided clear directions from lecturers, as well as a sense of guidance and support, facilitating students comfort and confidence during learning process. Engaging in teaching simulations in the classroom setting helped students feel more at ease, confident, and familiar with controlled learning environment that meets specific needs. This was consistent with Alt (2015), suggesting that students with low self-efficacy required guidance to succeed in academic tasks.

Prospective teachers with low self-efficacy faced challenges in analyzing various phenomena related to learning number concepts and planning activities due to lack of confidence in analytical abilities. There were also limitation in necessary abilities to design and compile effective learning tools during project planning and development. Similarly, during teaching practices with elementary schools, prospective teachers experienced anxiety and difficulty in collaborating and adapting to new situations. In product presentation and evaluation activities, students lacked confidence in delivering materials, which reduced presentation quality. There were also difficulties in handling criticism during evaluations, which were confirmations of shortcomings. According to Yildiz & Özdemir (2019), students with low self-efficacy developed a belief of "I will not succeed," leading to disengagement from mathematics learning tasks and negatively impacting learning outcomes. It is important to analyze the general perspective of the development activity; share the difficulties in the course of implementation; analyze each variable considered in the method; share and relate outcomes to the literature review; review the study objectives; reflect on topics interesting (e.g., how various aspects of the study may influence the results).

The conclusion should address the objectives outlined in the introduction, while explaining the reasons for any unachievable objectives. It was also crucial to show the limitations encountered during the study.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the results showed the positive impact of PjBL on PCK in mathematics education. PjBL, as a transformative pedagogical method, not only benefited students but also improved the professional development of educators. The effectiveness could be

attributed to fostering authentic and practical learning, motivation, support for learning independence, constructive activities, as well as the development of competencies and creation of flexible learning environment for students. This shift to student-centered learning was consistent with current educational ideals and had the potential to increase students' engagement and performance in mathematics. The results showed the importance of incorporating PjBL into teachers' training and professional development programs. The incorporation of PjBL into teachers' training and classroom practice could enhance mathematics education and create a more effective and student-centered learning environment. Aspiring educators might also benefit during training, while experienced educators could adopt the model to continually improve MPCK. Therefore, policymakers and educational institutions were recommended to consider incorporating PjBL into current teachers' preparation and professional development initiatives.

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